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Spam Email Detection using Neural Networks

SPEN

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Spam Email Detection using Neural Networks project, delivered in April 2025. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the "FAIR DATA" section.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values

EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
KB	Kilobyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Nicolas Bernal will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Spam Mails Dataset	Table	Tabular/CSV	< 5 MB	no
P2	Train Set	Subset	Tabular/CSV	< 5 MB	no
P3	Validation Set	Subset	Tabular/CSV	< 500 KB	no
P4	Test Set	Subset	Tabular/CSV	< 1 MB	no

Description for "Lemmatized Spam Ham Dataset":

Preprocessed data derived from the "Spam Mail" dataset, containing email messages labeled as spam or ham. Each record includes a unique identifier from the original "Spam Mail" dataset and an "experiment_id" indicating its assignment to a specific data split (training 70%, validation 10%, or test 20%) used in this experiment. The email content has been lemmatized and cleaned to remove noise such as punctuation, special characters, and stop words, ensuring consistent input for embedding and model training.

Description for "Train Set":

Train set from the "Spam Mails" dataset, consisting of 3619 random entries (70% of the total data). Entries in this set have experiment_id values ranging from 0 to 3618.

Description for "Validation Set":

Validation set from the "Spam Mails" dataset, consisting of 513 entries (10% of the total data). Entries in this set have experiment_id values ranging from 3619 to 4131.

Description for "Test Set":

Test set from the "Spam Mails" dataset, consisting of 1038 random entries (20% of the total data). Entries in this set have experiment_id values ranging from 4132 to 5170.

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Spam Mail	https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/venky73/spam-mails-dataset	CC0 1.0 Universal	no

Description for "Spam Mail":

The Spam Mail dataset is a collection of 5.171 emails that have been classified as spam or ham (non-spam). This dataset was originally created in 2006 for research purposes in the field of spam detection and filtering using machine learning techniques, specifically a Naive Bayes classifier as described in the paper "Spam Filtering with Naive Bayes - Which Naive Bayes?" by Metsis, Androutsopoulos, and Paliouras.

The data was created using mainly the inbox of 6 users of the company "Enron" for the "ham" emails, and the "spam" emails were collected from various sources, including the SpamAssassin corpus, the Honeypot project, the spam collection of Bruce Guenter, and spam collected by the authors themselves.

The emails were preprocessed to remove any html tags, and emails with non-latin characters were removed to avoid any possible bias since all "ham" emails are written with Latin characters. Also, all sensitive data was manually removed before including them in the data.

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The dataset was processed using Python 3.11.9, with libraries such as “pandas” (2.2.3) for data manipulation, “stanza” (1.10.1) for text lemmatization, and “nltk” (3.9.1) to remove English stop words. Tokenization of the text preprocessed emails is performed on demand using “scikit-learn” (1.6.1); however, the tokenized versions are not included in the final produced dataset.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

The dataset may be reused by students, educators, and researchers in the fields of Natural Language Processing (NLP), spam detection, machine learning model evaluation, and data preprocessing methodologies.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

We will make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository called DBRepo provided by TU WIEN. This repository provides a persistent identifier and metadata to explain the attributes of the data, how the data was proceeded and split, etc. DBRepo allows us to assign a Persistent Identifier (PID), specifically a DOI, to each dataset upon publication, ensuring long-term findability and stable referencing.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file at dataset and project levels. The README will explain all relevant information, including data fields, data generation processes, preprocessing methods, data splitting strategies, units of measurement (where applicable), and any important notes regarding data structure and interpretation.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or license when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow interdisciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests. Some datasets cannot be published and even need to be deleted at the end of the project. See section 5 for more details.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	No	28.04.2025	TU Wien's DBRepo	10.82556/bexb-5283	CC0-1.0
P2	Open	No	28.04.2025	TU Wien's DBRepo	10.82556/9caz-8j64	CC0-1.0
P3	Open	No	28.04.2025	TU Wien's DBRepo	10.82556/b67z-7d36	CC0-1.0
P4	Open	No	28.04.2025	TU Wien's DBRepo	10.82556/1qn4-mw15	CC0-1.0

Repository description:

DBRepo is a database repository operated by TU WIEN, designed to store, manage, and share research datasets. This repository assigns PID's (DOI's) to each dataset (including their tables, subsets, and views) ensuring long-term accessibility and stable referencing.

Data description:

The datasets generated in this project will be made openly available, as they currently do not contain any sensitive or personally identifiable information.

Accordingly, all datasets have been released under the CC0 1.0 Universal (Public Domain Dedication) license, allowing unrestricted public reuse.

In the future, if additional datasets are incorporated that may contain sensitive information, access restrictions (e.g., embargo periods) will be applied until appropriate data anonymization and cleaning processes are completed to ensure compliance with data protection regulations.

Metadata description:

All metadata associated with the datasets produced in this project will be made openly available and licensed under the CC0 1.0 Universal license, in full alignment with the requirements of the Grant Agreement and the FAIR principles. The metadata will include sufficient information to enable users to locate, access, and understand the datasets, including fields such as title, description, creators, license information, related identifiers, and access conditions.

2.3. Making data interoperable

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive README explaining what is the data composed of, where it comes from, and how it was processed. All datasets have been released under the CC0 1.0 Universal (Public Domain Dedication) license, allowing unrestricted public reuse.

Additionally, the GitHub repository contains source code and Jupyter notebooks used for data preprocessing, model training, evaluation, and output generation, all licensed under the **MIT License** to facilitate unrestricted reuse.

Research outputs apart from datasets, such as trained models and evaluation artifacts (confusion matrices, metrics, visualizations), are also openly shared via TUWRD under appropriate licenses and linked back to the datasets for full reproducibility.

Data quality checks will be done, e.g. checks of consistency of labels, logical errors in the data, data curation, and version control.

3. Other research outputs

In addition to the data generated during the experiment, the following research outputs have been produced:

1. Software artifacts

In a GitHub repository there are publicly available the two Jupyter notebooks created for data preprocessing (`data_processing.ipynb`) and model training (`spam_email_detector.ipynb`). These notebooks describe step by step how the produced data was generated how the final model was created.

The code is under the MIT licence; therefore, anyone can use it and modify it as their need. Also, comprehensive metadata is provided in the repository documenting the data sources, preprocessing steps, model hyperparameters, and experimental outputs.

The GitHub repository is available in this [link](#) or with the following DOI: [\[10.5281/zenodo.15298961\]](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15298961)

2. Trained model and evaluation reports

The trained spam classification model (`spam_classifier.h5`) and all evaluation artifacts—including performance metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score) and visualization outputs (confusion matrix and top 10 most frequent spam tokens)—have been stored in TUWRD.

TUWRD is the institutional repository of TU Wien for the storage and sharing of digital research objects. These artifacts are publicly accessible and are referenced with the following DOI: [\[10.70124/kzhm9-md089\]](https://doi.org/10.70124/kzhm9-md089). A detailed README file is included in the repository, to explain the contents and intended usage of each file to support reusability.

4. Allocation of resources

No significant direct costs are expected for making the data and research outputs FAIR in this project. Storage, archiving, persistent identifier assignment (DOI), and long-term preservation are provided by TU Wien through institutional services such as DBRepo and TUWRD at no additional cost to the researcher. Also, the infrastructure to store the code related to this project (GitHub) does not generate additional costs as long as the repository remains within the free usage limits.

Indirect costs mainly consist of personnel time dedicated to data management activities, including metadata creation, repository submissions, regular backup reviews, and maintaining documentation.

The Data Manager responsible for overseeing the data management activities is Nicolas Bernal (TU Wien, ORCID: 0009-0006-0344-0652). He is responsible for fulfilling the FAIR principles, managing submissions to repositories, supervising backup procedures, and coordinating versioning and metadata updates.

Long-term preservation is guaranteed through the policies of TU Wien's repositories. Datasets will be preserved for 10 to 20 years, depending on their scientific importance, as detailed in the Long-Term Preservation section. Decisions regarding data retention periods, necessary updates, or eventual archiving actions will be made by the project team in coordination with TU Wien's Center for Research Data Management if necessary.

5. Data security

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

All data generated in this project is stored in institutional repositories managed by TU Wien: DBRepo for datasets and TUWRD for research outputs such as trained models and evaluation reports.

To ensure the protection and recoverability of the stored data on DBRepo:

- Automatic weekly backups of all databases are scheduled using a customized backup service based on mysqldump procedures optimized for MariaDB using options such as --skip-lock-tables.
- Also, the project team will hold monthly backup review to analyse and determine whether older versions can be safely deleted or not. This procedure will be done manually to avoid unintended data loss and to maintain control over critical research records.

Regarding TUWRD, TU Wien ensures the physical security of research outputs by maintaining two separate replicas of the repositories. Data recovery mechanisms and disaster recovery plans are in place, operated by Campus IT. Additionally, data preservation is handled at multiple levels:

- Physical preservation (Level 1): Ensuring bit-level integrity of files.
- Logical preservation (Level 2): Migration of file formats if they become obsolete.
- Semantic preservation (Level 3): Available under specific curation agreements, if required.

Once data is published and assigned a Persistent Identifier (DOI), it cannot be modified or deleted. Updates to the files require creating a new version of the record, ensuring traceability and reproducibility.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. However, if in the future new datasets containing personal or sensitive data are included, appropriate anonymization and security measures will be implemented before any storage or sharing actions. If this happens, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	reading only
P2	writing	reading only	reading only
P3	writing	reading only	reading only
P3	writing	reading only	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	DBRepo (Data repository provided by TU WIEN)	20 years
P2	DBRepo (Data repository provided by TU WIEN)	10 years
P3	DBRepo (Data repository provided by TU WIEN)	10 years
P4	DBRepo (Data repository provided by TU WIEN)	10 years

The main processed dataset (P1), which is the foundational data for all experiments, will be preserved for 20 years to support future reuse, verification, and (potential) extensions of the research.

The subsets created for the initial experiment (P2, P3, and P4) will be preserved for 10 years, which is enough to guarantee reproducibility of the original experiment while avoiding unnecessary long-term storage cost from maintaining this data.

6. Ethical and legal issues

6.1. Personal data

Currently, no personal data is processed in this project. The reused dataset (R1 - Spam Mail) was previously preprocessed by its original creators to remove all personal and sensitive information, ensuring full anonymization of “ham” emails. Therefore, the produced datasets (P1, P2, P3, P4) derived from R1 also do not contain any personally identifiable information.

However, as new data (emails) is included in this project it will become necessary for us to ensure compliance with data protection laws, by anonymization of personal data for preservation and/or sharing.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and rights of use

All datasets generated and reused within the project are under open licenses (CC0 1.0 Universal). The project leader (Nicolas Bernal, TU Wien) and other members of the project hold the rights and control access to the datasets produced in this project. Public sharing of produced datasets is ensured via persistent identifiers and repositories (DBRepo, TUWRD).

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.